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BRAND ATTRACTIVENESS: AN IMPERATIVE FOR WORSHIPPERS' SATISFACTION OF MAJOR PENTECOSTAL CHURCHES IN PORT HARCOURT

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study was to investigate the relationship between brand attractiveness and satisfaction of worshippers of major Pentecostal Churches in Port Harcourt. The study adopted cross-sectional survey design in accessing the research elements. The population of the research consists of worshippers of Pentecostal Churches in Port Harcourt. Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficient tool was used to test the 2 proposed hypotheses. Result from this process indicated that there is a positive and significant relationship between brand attractiveness and worshippers' satisfaction. The study therefore concludes that, worshippers of Pentecostal churches tend to identify with their churches due to how unique & friendly their officials are, and the services ambient attributes that reflect their (worshippers) self-image concept. Based on the conclusion, the study recommends that authorities of Pentecostal churches are encouraged to do more in offering services that reflect worshippers' self-image concept. This is due to the fact that worshippers' feel that by identifying with services of the church that demonstrate similar self-definition, will result to positive service experience and worshippers' satisfaction. This therefore explains that worshippers usually maintain some level of spiritual stability to services that are in congruent with self-concept, and this positively leads to worshippers' referral.

KEYWORDS

Spiritual Marketing, Brand Attractiveness, Worshippers' Satisfaction, Service Friendliness.

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Introduction

Over the last 20 years, Nigeria has witnessed a huge growth in both new and existing charismatic Pentecostal orientation (Egbulefu, 2016). Nigerian Pentecostal churches play crucial role in motivating and influencing the socio-political and economic life of the people within communities (Akanbi & Beyers, 2017). Pentecostalism movement exerts a cultural influence so deep that it has, in effect, become a defining factor of the country's major civilisations. According to Warner (2018), Pentecostalism is one of the most rapidly growing movements in Nigeria, with approximately 80 million adherents.

In addition, Diara & Onah (2014) opined that Pentecostal churches are in most cases the outcome of separation of groups of members from the orthodox or mainline churches, such as the Roman Catholic, Anglican, Presbyterian, Methodist, and Baptist churches. Insinuations have been made that Pentecostal churches in Nigeria became prominent after the country's independence in 1960, as there are no records of a Pentecostal church existing before then. In this regard, Diara & Onah (2014) opined that the political independence encouraged religious independence in the country, giving rise to a situation whereby the strong tie of membership of the mainline churches was loosened due to their "lose attitude" to Bible reading as opposed to the Roman Catholic Church which restricted Bible reading to the priests. Consequently, some Christians began to see themselves more as individual Christians than as part of the corporate body, the church. Hence, the beginning of new independent Christian groups with evangelical and Pentecostal persuasions, most of which turn around and become churches later (Owoeye 2006).

Despite the successes recorded by churches within in the last few years, however competition from rival ministries is constantly becoming more challenging, requiring management of these organizations to strategically position their brands in the minds of worshippers (Davis, Schoenbau & Audet, 2018). This entails that management of faith-based organizations must rejig their service delivery strategies in ways that better appeal to the psychology and/or emotions of worshippers if they are prepared to compete favourably in the spiritual market. Though, the core fundamentals of spiritual marketing are arguably the same today as they were years ago, however, what has changed is that the spiritual market has become so saturated that the most successful religious organizations have now understood the importance of deploying branding strategies to distinguish themselves from competitors, which is in line with contemporary marketing management initiatives for faith-based organization (Amazu, Simon & Anis, 2019). As spiritual needs of the people grow, the opportunities for churches to take advantage of this trend by providing superior service that are attractive to worshippers emerges. Hence, the need to provide services with attractive identity where service attributes match worshippers' self-concept.

According to Holt (2005), when the service delivery is in congruent with the worshippers' personal value, it is expected that the individual would prefer such service offering in comparison with competitors' offerings. Brand-worshipper value congruence corresponds to what Bhattacharya & Sen (2003) conceptualized as important element that derives perceived attractiveness. According to Sirgy (2001), religious organizations which are notably attractive to worshippers provide benefits similar to those received where service satisfaction is evident, whereas organizations who possess high connectedness are generally seen to be complimentary to worshippers' self-concept as their services assist in the maintenance of self-consistency, self-esteem and self-relevance of worshippers. Worshippers usually feel that by identifying with a church that is attractive may result to positive service experience, satisfaction and loyalty (Agu, 2002).

More so, worshippers usually maintain some level of psychological stability and associate themselves with churches they perceive as attractive even to other users (Gel, 2005). In addition, Amazu et al. (2019) related conceptualized service attractiveness from the area of service friendly by organizations at several service encounters. The authors mentioned that when people perceive a high level of friendly services on the part of church officials; they will always want to come back to such organization due to previous positive service experience. To corroborate with this thought, Marin & de Maya (2013) expressed that service friendliness is one of the importance components of brand attractiveness, and has a huge influence on worshippers' satisfaction, referral and loyalty. Also, Davis et al. (2018) opined that brand attractiveness could also come from its physical environment/surrounding in terms of ambient condition, temperature, and other aesthetic features. Hence, the smell, functionality, interior deco', etc could have a great impact on worshippers' revisit actions especially where there is high congruence between worshippers' self-concept matches with the psychological implications of the physical surroundings of the church.

In addition, studies have been conducted in the area of brand attractiveness and customer purchase behaviour both in product and service-related industries. Currás-Pérez, Bigné-Alcañiz, & Alvarado-Herrera (2009) examined brand attractiveness from the perspective customer brand identity in the telecom market. The authors stressed that strong brand identity clears the road for customers to perceive the brand as having attractive components. Marin & de Maya (2013) who investigated the role of brand attractiveness and personal connection in the restaurant sub-sector, used physical surroundings such as ambient condition and temperature as a way of measuring brand attractiveness, and these constructs were combined to evaluate their impact on customer purchase intention. In addition, Rinalini & Anubhuti (2019) linked brand attractiveness for brand personality in the aviation sector. The authors developed a conceptual framework involving variables such as service friendliness, interior deco' and electronic ticketing; in impacting passengers' re-purchase attitude. However, in view of the above studies and other related ones, this research departed from extant studies by combining service friendliness and ambient attributes as dimensions of brand attractiveness, with a view to examining their effect on worshippers' satisfaction as it relates to Salvation Ministry Church, Port Harcourt.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this research is to empirically examine the relationship between brand attractiveness and worshippers' satisfaction of major Pentecostal Churches in Port Harcourt. However, the specific objectives are to:

- (i) Examine the relationship between service friendliness and satisfaction of worshippers of major Pentecostal Churches in Port Harcourt.
- (ii) Investigate the relationship between ambient attributes and satisfaction of worshippers of major Pentecostal Churches in Port Harcourt.

Fig 1.1: Conceptual Framework on Brand Attractiveness and worshippers' Referral

Source: Rinalini & Anubhuti (2019).

Literature Review

Theoretical Framework

The theories upon which this research was anchored are Social Identification Theory (SIT). SIT is an integral part of one's self-concept. Individuals' social identity is basically derived from the social entity they associate themselves with (Lam, 2012). These social entities include religious group, demographic groups, educational institutions, traditional institutions, occupation, etc. According to Bhattacharya (2001), the SIT holds that people tend to simplify the social world by identifying themselves with like minds as they form a social group. The author went on to state that this social identification or categorization not only help individuals to cognitively segment and order the social environment, but also, provide them with better ways of defining themselves and the social groups they belong to. From a psychological point of view, social identification means that a person identifies him or herself as a member of a society. An expression of identification with an organization is treated as special types of social identification (Bhattacharya & Sens (2003).

From a religious point of view, Scott & Lane, (2000) draw from the SIT to examine the concept of worshippers-church identification and their unique features that bring about the symbiotic relationship both parties share. The authors argued that churches with unique and meaningful social identity may have the will to fulfil worshippers' key self-definitional need. Also, the study of Martins & Maya (2013) proposes that worshippers identify with brands that share similar symbolic meaning, in which worshippers perceive a mechanism to maintain their identity.

Concept of Brand Attractiveness

Literature on brand attractiveness is few and recent studies on the construct have demonstrated its impact on consumer purchase behaviour (Bhattacharya & Sen, 2003; Marin et al., 2009; Holt, 2005). According to the Oxford dictionary, "attractiveness" means the quality of being pleasing or appealing to the senses, also the possession of qualities or features that arouse interest. Brand attractiveness is considered as a powerful, intangible force, which goes much beyond the physical aesthetics of a brand (Alden, Steenkamp & Batra, 2000). It is an invisible, overwhelming pull, which subliminally, but irresistibly draws audiences towards itself (Holt, 2005). Brand attractiveness according to Marin et al (2009), refers to customers' evaluation of service offering distinctive and enduring association.

In addition, Marin et al. (2009) stated that the attractiveness of a brand measures the extent to which customers perceive other users of the brand to be similar in terms of lifestyle and responding uniquely to marketing programs. The authors further stated that the underlying components of brand attractiveness such as nice surrounding, friendly service etc, can help a service organization dictate customer purchase actions. Brand attractiveness is customers' positive evaluation of the brand's identity in relation to how it helps consumers fulfil their self-definitional needs (Currás-Pérez, Bigné-Alcañiz, & Alvarado-Herrera, 2009).

From a religious perspective, worshippers tend to identify with churches they perceive as attractive by self-image concept. Worshippers usually feel that by identifying with a church that is attractive may result to positive service experience (Agu, 2002). More so, followers of church activities usually maintain some level of psychology stability and associate themselves with religious organizations they perceive as attractive even to other people (Gel, 2005).

Satisfaction

The concept of customer satisfaction is multi-dimensional construct. In this sense, Bitner (2010) distinguished between satisfaction with the organization, core service, and the contact staff which the authors refer as salespersons. However, it is important to state that this research focuses on customer satisfaction with the bank and the core services offered by salespersons. These services include; investment funds, pensions, mortgages, life insurance, and credit cards. Since salespersons are the firm in the customers' eyes; firms must strive to ensure that salespersons are equipped with the necessary skills and technical know-how in interacting with the target market. This is undertaken to cordial relationship with as well as satisfying customers. According to Zeithaml & Berry (2003), customer experience with organizations is a strategic insight in analysing customer satisfaction. The authors opined that satisfaction is an emotional reaction that originates from customer evaluation of perceived discrepancy between prior performance expectation and actual service experience.

Customer satisfaction is one of the widely discussed concepts in the consumer behaviour literature. Superior service offering and enhanced customer satisfaction are very crucial component leading to the organisational success (Choi & Chu, 2001). Customer satisfaction is defined as a post consumption evaluative judgment with respect to specific service offerings. It is the outcome of an evaluative process that relates to pre-purchase expectations with service performance during and after the consumption experience (Giese & Cote, 2010).

Empirical Review

Brand Attractiveness and Satisfaction

Many studies have investigated the association between branding strategies and consumer purchase behaviour. Chaudhuri & Holbrook (2001) examined the influence of branding and its dimensions on consumer satisfaction. The study was conducted on a sample of 428 Polish consumers of sports apparel brands who completed an online survey. The results were processed using exploratory factor analysis, Spearman's rank-order correlation coefficient (Spearman's Rho), and logistic regression analysis. Findings demonstrated that branding plays a vital role in consumer buying behaviour and has a positive effect on consumer satisfaction.

Service Friendliness and Satisfaction

According to Agu (2002), service friendliness is an effective display from staff of an organization towards customers in the service encounter or interaction. The author argued that service friendliness can be described as a range of behaviour including familiarity, flirting, caring, politeness, responsiveness, helpfulness and understanding. Also, Gel (2005) stated that service friendliness portrays a sense of importance as perceived by customer and plays a critical role in determining a positive service outcome.

Researchers have examined the relationship between service friendliness and satisfaction. Among the many researchers that have carried out such studies; Marin et al. (2009) found out that courtesy and care which was adopted as dimensions of service friendliness had positive and significantly related to customer repeat purchase and referral. Currás-Pérez et al.(2009) found out that contact staff friendliness in retail context and how shoppers perceive the outcome of their interaction was confirmed to be the fundamental reasons shoppers return for further shopping or never return to the supermarket and switching to other organization. While defining service friendliness as being caring, patient, and helpful to customers by employees of an organization, as both parties interact in an exchange relationship; Solomon & Robinson (2008) found out that staff friendliness has a significant

effect on positive word-of-mouth communication, store traffic, and customer loyalty. Chaudhuri, A., & Holbrook (2001) who emphasized on the importance of service friendliness in building competitive advantage in the retail market; found out that act of courtesy and empathy are critical element in improving customer patronage.

In addition, Salamon & Robinson (2008) revealed how service friendliness can be used in winding customer complaints and simultaneously converting dissatisfied customers to loyal once. The author stated that service friendliness has been confirmed by many researchers as crucial management tool to commanding and directing consumer endorsement. Further, the authors found out that service friendliness has a positive and huge impact on consumer purchase behaviour. More so, Halim & Hard (2005) argued that service friendliness is of significant interest among strategists' business practices. They found that effective service friendliness leads to enhanced store traffic, which in-turn helps the spread of positive word-of-mouth to other people. In the light of these postulates, we state the hypothesis below:

H₀₁: Service friendliness has no significant relationship with worshippers' referral of major Pentecostal Churches in Port Harcourt.

Ambient Attributes and Satisfaction

Ambient attributes are the critical facet of physical environment. Ambient conditions in the religious sector are of great importance as most worshippers want/desire to have comfort and well-being experiences while receiving service (Demoulin & Willems, 2019). Ambient attributes of a place along with other physical environment factors irrefutably play a key role in boosting comfortable service experiences by offering spiritual and psychological/emotional well-being. According to Han (2013), ambient attributes are background environmental stimuli, which influence peoples' perceptions, senses, or affective responses. Air conditions (e.g., air freshness, dust-free, fresh odour), noise level, and temperature (e.g., dryness/humidity, hot/cold) are crucial constituents of ambient attributes (Han, 2013).

Studies on ambient attributes have either a positive or negative effect on customer purchase behaviour. Several authors have identified ambient attributes as a factor that affects perceptions of human responses to the environment (e.g., Bitner, 2001; Xu & Gursoy, 2020). Ambient attributes encompass an array of background characteristics of the environment such as temperature, lighting, noise, music, and scent (Zeithaml and Bitner, 2003). As a general rule ambient attributes affect five senses. Some authors relate ambient conditions to atmospherics (Xu & Gursoy, 2020). The authors in their study found that smell is significantly related with repeat visit intentions. Some scent provokes basic emotional reactions because the olfactory lobe is actually part of the limbic system (Bitner, 2001). Other ambient attributes like nose are directly connected to the olfactory lobe and the limbic system Bitner (2001) found that noise had a positive influence on referral behaviour.

In addition, Sirgy. & Su (2016), ambient attributes trigger a positive affective evaluation of customer service/product experiences and increase favourable behavioural intentions for a place (e.g., revisit intention). The authors found that ambient attributes are the crucial predictors of cognitive and emotional factors and the important contributors to approach decisions. Headley & Miller (2012) who examined the impact of ambience conditions on customer satisfaction in the restaurant industry; found out that interior decor' such as lightning and music had a positive and strong correlation ($r=0.884$) with customer satisfaction. In view of these postulates, we state the hypothesis below:

H₀₂: Ambient attribute has no significant relationship with worshippers' referral of major Pentecostal Churches in Port Harcourt.

Methodology

The focus of this study was to examine the nature of relationship between brand attractiveness and worshippers' loyalty of Salvation Ministries in Port Harcourt; therefore, quasi-experimental design was used to access its study elements. It is important to mention that due focus on Salvation ministry as a church, this research used case study approach in obtaining data from respondents. Hence, questionnaire distribution was used to elicit information from members/worshippers of the Church.

Basically, this study focused on residents of Port Harcourt due to the fact that major Pentecostal churches are located in the city. Again, based on the researchers sincere observation that most resident of Rivers State are predominantly Christians and a few Muslims, not ruling out the presence of other religions, however, just very minimal. It was against this backdrop this research was limited to worshippers of Pentecostal churches in Port Harcourt metropolis. On this premise, the population of this research consists of worshippers/members of Pentecostal churches in Port Harcourt. However, it is crucial to note that, to the best of the researchers' knowledge, no known document/data on the exact number of members/worshippers of major Pentecostal churches who resides in the city. Based on the above, the researcher considered the population of Port Harcourt as the study's population. Available records reveal that Port Harcourt has a population of three million, three hundred and twenty-five thousand (3,325,000) (<https://worldpopulationreview.com>). More so, while it is important to state that the study focused on members/worshippers of major Pentecostal churches within the city; however, available records show that there are sixteen (16) major Pentecostal churches in Port Harcourt (<https://ng.africabz.com/rivers/pentecostal-church>). In no particular order, the table below further explains this point:

Table 1 Major Pentecostal Churches in Port Harcourt

S/N	Name of Church	Address of Church (Head or Regional Quarter)
1.	House on the Rock	Plot F, 23 Sani Abacha Road, GRA phase III, Port Harcourt.
2.	The Kings Assembly	58 Tombia Extension, GRA Phase III, Port Harcourt.
3.	Gateway International Church	30/32 Elioparanwo Road, Off Ada-George Road, Port Harcourt.
4.	Living Faith Church	4 Kaduna Street, D-Line Port Harcourt.
5.	Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG)	2B Degema Close, Obia Port Harcourt.
6.	Dominion City Church	Along NTA/Choba Road, Port Harcourt.
7.	The Carpenter's Church	The Carpenter's Drive, Off Agip Road Rumueme, Mile 4, Port Harcourt.
8.	Deeper Life Bible Church	East-West Road Atali, Port Harcourt.
9.	Omega Power Ministries (OPM)	Doctor Jesus City, Mbodo Aluu, Port Harcourt.
10.	Salvation Ministries	Plot 17 Birabi Street, GRA Phase II, Port Harcourt.
11.	Royal House of Grace	13 Graceland Avenue, Off Civic Centre Junction, Rumueme, Port Harcourt.
12.	Christ Embassy	58 Psychiatric Hospital Road, Rumuigbo Road, Port Harcourt.

		Harcourt.
13.	Church of God Mission International	34 Church of God Mission International Road, Port Harcourt.
14.	Mountain of Fire Miracle Church	213 Aba Express Road, Rumuola, Port Harcourt.
15.	Dunamis International Gospel Centre	3 Maxwel Adoki Street, Off Peter Odili Road, Port Harcourt.
16.	Bible Faith Church	5 Olu Obasanjo Road, Off Water-Line Junction, Port Harcourt.

Source: Research Desk, 2023.

This study adopted judgmental sampling technique, as the researchers used their discretion and experience in selecting samples for the study. In addition, the study used the Taro Yamen formula in determining its sample size. By applying this formula with a population size of 3,325,000 and a significance level of 0.005; a sample size of 400 was arrived at. This meant that a total of 400 worshippers/members were conveniently selected across the major 16 churches, and were administered copies of the research instrument. It is important to mention that each church received a total of 25 copies of questionnaire.

In addition, both primary and secondary sources of data were used. While the former was obtained with the help of questionnaire; the latter was gotten from sources such as journal articles, internet publications, magazines, etc. More so, the variables involved, alongside their various statement items were measured on a 5-point Likert-scale ranging from Strongly Agree (5-points), Agree (4-points), Not Sure (3-points), Disagree (2-points), and Strongly Disagree (1point).

In validating the instrument for data collection, the researchers used expert checking in the field of management and marketing. Further validation was drawn from literature review sources on the various dimensions and measures. Also, Cronbach' Alpha coefficient test was used in order to check the consistency of the instrument with acceptable benchmark of 0.7 (70%) and upward. Lastly, at the primary level, descriptive statistical tools such as tables, percentages, etc, were used to analyse the demographic profile of respondents. On the other hand, Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficient was adopted at the secondary level of analysis to test the two proposed hypotheses for this research. However, all analyses were carried out with the help of SPSS (version 21.0).

Results and Discussions

The focus of this chapter was to analyse and present data that were obtained from the field.

Data Presentation

Table 2: Showing Questionnaire Distribution Results

Questionnaire	Frequency	Percentage
Distributed Copies	397	100
Returned Copies	380	96
Not returned Copies	17	4
Returned and useful Copies	366	92

Source: Survey Data, 2023, SPSS 22 Output.

Table 2 showed that a total of three hundred and ninety-seven (397) copies of the questionnaire were distributed, out of which three hundred and eighty (380) copies representing a response rate of 96% were retrieved and seventeen (17) which represented 4% were not retrieved. Out of the ones that were retrieved, three hundred and sixty-six (366) which represent 92% were correctly filled and used for this research.

Reliability Test Results

The table below shows the summary of reliability statistics. This test includes the dimensions and measures of both independent and dependent variables as indicated below.

Table 3: Summary of Reliability Analysis

Constructs	Cronbach Alpha
Service Friendliness	0.849
Ambient Attributes	0.892
Referral	0.809

Source: Cronbach Alpha Output, 2023.

Based on the above table, Cronbach's Alpha value for service friendliness was 0.849, while ambient attribute and referral were 0.892 and 0.809. This indicated that all Cronbach's Alpha values for each construct was more than 0.70. Thus, it can be concluded that all items for each construct in this research were in the range of 'good' and 'very good' which showed high stability, consistent results and also in the satisfactory level.

Testing of Hypotheses

Test of Hypothesis One (H₀₁): Service friendliness has no significant relationship with worshippers' referral of major Pentecostal Churches in Port Harcourt.

Table 4: Correlation Analysis showing the relationship between Service Friendliness and Referral of Worshippers

			Correlations	
			Service Friendliness	Referral
Spearman's rho	Service Friendliness	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.904
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	366	366
	Referral	Correlation Coefficient	.904	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	366	366

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Survey Data, 2023, SPSS 22 Output.

Decision: Table 4.3 above reveals a Spearman Rank Correlation Coefficient of 0.904 and probability value of 0.000. This result indicates that there is a positive and significant relationship between service friendliness and referral of worshippers of Pentecostal churches in Port Harcourt. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis, because the PV (0.000) <0.05 level of significance.

Test of Hypothesis Two (H₀₂): Ambient attribute has no significant relationship with worshippers' referral of major Pentecostal Churches in Port Harcourt.

Table 5: Correlation Analysis showing the relationship between Ambient Attributes and Referral of Worshippers

		Correlations	
		Ambient Attributes	Referral
Spearman's rho	Ambient Attributes	Correlation Coefficient	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
		N	366
	Referral	Correlation Coefficient	.891*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
		N	366

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Survey Data, 2023, SPSS 22 Output

Decision: Table 4.4 above reveals a Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficient of 0.891 and probability value of 0.000. This result indicates that there is a positive and significant relationship between ambient attributes and referral of Pentecostal Churches in Port Harcourt. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis, because the PV (0.000) <0.05 level of significance.

Discussion of Findings

Based on the results, this section observed relationships among variables used, and were discussed with regards to the findings of previous studies.

Positive Relationship between Service Friendliness and Referral

Hypothesis one (H₀₁) was designed to determine the significant relationship between service friendliness and referral. The hypothesis was tested using Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficient, and result showed that a significant relationship exists between both variables (Rho = 0.904). Our analysis revealed the existence of positive and significant relationship between service friendliness and referral. This result was in agreement with the study of Solomon & Robinson (2008) when the authors revealed how service friendliness can be used in winding customer complaints and simultaneously converting dissatisfied customers to loyal once. The author stated that service friendliness has been confirmed by many researchers as crucial management tool to commanding and directing consumer endorsement. Further, the authors found out that service friendliness has a positive and huge impact on consumer purchase behaviour. More so, Halim & Hard (2005) argued that service

friendliness is of significant interest among strategists' business practices. They found that effective service friendliness leads to enhanced store traffic, which in-turn helps the spread of positive word-of-mouth to other people.

Positive Relationship between Ambient Attributes and Referral

In H_{02} , ambient attribute was statistically tested against referral using Spearman Rank Correlation Coefficient. Hypothesis two aimed at examining the relationship extent between ambient attributes and referral. The result showed the existence of significant relationship between both variables ($Rho=0.891$). Our analysis revealed the existence of positive and significant relationship between ambient attributes and worshippers' referral. This finding was however consistent with the study of Sirgy. & Su (2016), when they mentioned that ambient attributes trigger a positive affective evaluation of customer service/product experiences and increase favourable behavioural intentions for a place (e.g., revisit intention). The authors found that ambient attributes are the crucial predictors of cognitive and emotional factors and the important contributors to approach decisions. Headley & Miller (2012) who examined the impact of ambiance conditions on customer satisfaction in the health care industry; found out that interior decor' such as lightning and music had a positive and strong correlation ($r=0.884$) with customer satisfaction.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the findings of the research, we conclude as follows:

- i. Generally, worshippers in Pentecostal Ministries tend to identify with the church due to how the unique friendly services and ambient reflect their (worshippers) self-image concept. Worshippers feel that by identifying with the church results to positive service experience. This therefore explains why worshippers usually maintain some level of psychology and spiritual stability and associate themselves with the church because they perceive the friendliness of church officials as attractive.
- ii. In addition, service friendliness is more crucial in handling worshippers' complaints or dissatisfaction. Therefore, it is fundamental in building church-worshipper symbiotic relationship. This means that friendly disposition of church officials towards their members has helped the church improve worshippers' satisfaction and referral.
- iii. The desire to have comfort and well-being experiences while receiving treatment is one of the strategic reasons ambient attributes has become an important factor that shape and direct worshippers' satisfaction and referral. In this way physical surrounding factors in the church irrefutably play a key role in boosting positive service experiences and offering psychological and spiritual well-being to worshippers.

It was with respect of the above conclusions, this research advanced the following recommendations:

- i. Authorities of Pentecostal ministries are encouraged to do more in offering services that reflect worshippers' self-image concept. They should be friendly in their dealings or interactions with members. This is due to the fact that worshippers' feel delighted when services are friendly, which in-turn result to positive service experience and worshippers' referral. This therefore explains that worshippers usually maintain some level of spiritual stability, and this positively leads to worshippers' satisfaction and referral.
- ii. Also, church officials should endeavor to create a friendly atmosphere where service personnel such as ushers, protocol/security officials, etc, have a friendly disposition towards worshippers. This is strategic because it leads to improved worshippers' satisfaction and referral actions.

- iii. *Lastly, church authorities may consider investing more in ambient attributes such as lightening, sounds, good parking arrangement, and other items that make the service surroundings more comfortable and attractive to worshippers, as this research has proven their strategic prowess to evoking worshippers' satisfaction, and which in-turn encourage them to pass the good message about the church to others.*

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